

CURRENT WATER AVAILABILITY AND ITS EFFICIENCY USE IN AGRICULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN: A REVIEW

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Abstract. *Uzbekistan, a landlocked country in Central Asia, is in the center and mainly between two major rivers the Syr Darya and the Amu Darya. Nowadays, Uzbekistan faces significant challenges in water resource management, specifically in the agriculture sector, which takes almost 90 percent of total water usage. This paper will look at the current state water availability in Uzbekistan, by bringing to the fore to regional disparities, dependence on transboundary water sources, and impact of climate change on water supply. Further research examines the adoption of water-saving technologies such as drip irrigation, sprinkled irrigation, laser land leveling, and regulated deficit irrigation, assessing their cost-effectiveness and scope within different zones.*

Keywords: *agriculture, water efficiency, climate change, water supply, water-saving technologies, cost-effectiveness.*

Intruduction

Uzbekistan, with the area of 448,978 km² double landlocked country located in the Irano-Turanian bottomlands of Central Asia. The country has various physical and geographical conditions, with arid and semi-arid plains by covering 78.8% of the central and northwest regions and mountains comprising 21.2% of the southern, southeastern, and eastern areas (Sadykov, 1975). Also, Uzbekistan borders with five countries: Kazakhstan – to the north and northwest border length is 2330 km the longest bordering country, Turkmenistan – southwest border length 1793 km, Tajikistan – southeast border length 1312 km, Kyrgyzstan – northeast border length 1314 km and Afghanistan – border length 144 km the shortest bordering country. The lands of Uzbekistan can be divided into 3 major parts (Figure 1): western, central and eastern parts.

Climate

The climate of Uzbekistan is sharply continental and impacted by its location within the Eurasian continent and topography. We can divide country's territory into two parts: 1) western-northern territories are mostly flat, open to cold air masses, resulting in hot summers and cold winters. 2) The southern part is well covered by mountains ranges, including the Himalayas, Hindi Kush, Pamir, and Tien Shan, which block moisture from the Indian Ocean, the closest significant source of humidity (Hamidov et al., 2020). Arid and semi-arid regions of Uzbekistan experience low level of precipitation, which significantly influence the country's climate, water availability, agriculture productivity, socio-economic conditions and ecosystems. In plains, average precipitation ranges from 100 to 200 mm in plains, while mountains slopes might receive up to 600 to 900 mm, predominantly during the winter and spring (Duulatov et al., 2019). The average rainfall in Uzbekistan is estimated within 200 mm per year. This limited natural moisture is a critical factor shaping ecological systems and the need for comprehensive water resources management. The climate in plains face long, hot summers and cold winters, at

the same time as the mountainous regions exhibiting temperature variations influenced by elevation, relief, and slope direction.

Figure 1. Geographical map of Uzbekistan

The seasonal precipitation in spring and winter, with low rainfall during the hot summer months, straightly corresponds with the development and reduction of vegetation in the deserts and plains. Despite the subsequent strong summer heat quickly evaporates the limited moisture in regions (Gerlitz & Khaydarov, 2019). The country’s arid and semi-arid places directly result of the minimal and uneven distribution of precipitation during the year (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Aridity index of Uzbekistan

Source: Food Security and Sustainable Development in the Turkic States

< 0.03 Hyper arid; 0.03 – 0.2 Arid; 0.2 - 0.5 Semi-arid; 0.5 – 0.65 Dry sub-humid; > 0.65 Humid

In these arid regions, rivers valleys serve as the main hubs for human habitation and agricultural activities, sustained by the irrigation provided by Uzbekistan’s major rivers: the Amu Darya, Syr Darya, Zarafshan, Kashkadarya, Chirchik and Ahangaran rivers serve as the

main living areas for the country’s living areas for population (Kalashnikova et al., 2023: Bissenbayeva, 2020: Karthe et al., 2017: Hamidov et al., 2018) (Figure 3 and Figure 4).

Figure 3. Land use classification of the Uzbekistan

Source: Food Security and Sustainable Development in the Turkic States

The rivers valleys of Uzbekistan are more than just centres of farming, they're the cultural and historical heart of the country. For over 2000 years people have lived and thrived here, building irrigation systems that turned dry land into fertile fields. The network of canals, ditches and drains tells the story of generations who learned to manage water wisely, grow a variety of crops and build their lives around the rivers (Efficient Irrigation and Water Conservation in Central Asia, n.d.).

Figure 4. Overview of the Uzbekistan natural land cover

Source: Food Security and Sustainable Development in the Turkic States

Water availability

In Uzbekistan, water comes from a mix of natural sources like surface and groundwater, as well as from human activity, such as return flows from irrigated fields. Most of the country's waters resources are part of the larger Aral Sea Basin and are shared with neighbouring countries

making them transboundary by nature (Figure 5). Among the major rivers, only the Kashkadarya and Ahangaran are fully contained within Uzbekistan borders. The other rivers flow in and out of the country multiple times, so measuring total water inflow and usage can't be done in isolation. Instead, water calculations must be made at the basin level, considering not just the overall flow, but also water-sharing agreements and actual usage within Uzbekistan itself.

Figure 5. Aral Sea Basin and Transboundary River share inputs

Source: Food Security and Sustainable Development in the Turkic States

From a hydrological perspective, surface runoff in the region can be divided into three main zones. First, there's the *flow formation zone*, located in the upper watersheds of mountainous areas in the southeast — including parts of Afghanistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan. Next is the *flow transit and dissipation zone*, which stretches across the central areas of Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan. Finally, there are the *delta zones* in the northwest, also involving parts of Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan. Effectively managing the region's water resources — especially those from transboundary rivers — is essential for addressing the challenges of the arid climate. It's key to maintaining sustainable agriculture and preserving the region's ecosystems. According to estimates, the total available surface water in the basin is around 116.5 billion cubic meters per year (Table 1). However, only about 10% of this amount originates within Uzbekistan's territory. In addition to surface water, the region also holds about 31.17 billion cubic meters of groundwater, with 14.7 billion in the Amu Darya Basin and 16.4 billion in the Syr Darya Basin (Glantz, n.d.: Leng et al., 2021)

Table 1. Total annual river flow formation in the Aral Sea Basin

Country	10 ⁹ m ³			%
	Syr Darya	Amu Darya	Area Sea basin	Aral Sea Basin
Kazakhstan	2.426	–	2.426	2.1
Kyrgyz Republic	27.605	1.604	29.209	25.1
Turmenistan	–	1.549	1.549	1.2
Tadjikistan	1.005	49.898	50.585	43.4
Uzbekistan	6.167	4.736	11.223	9.6
Afghanistan & Iran	–	21.593	21.593	18.6
Total of Aral Sea Basin	37.203	79.380	116.585	100.0

The Amu Darya is the region’s largest river in terms of water volume. It stretches for about 2,540 kilometers and has a catchment area of 309,000 square kilometers. Its journey begins at the Vakhjir Pass glacier in Afghanistan, initially flowing as the Panj River before merging with the Vakhsh River — fed by sources in Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan (Sokolov, 1999). Along its course, the Amu Darya forms natural borders between Afghanistan, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan, and further downstream, it separates Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan before eventually flowing toward the Aral Sea. The river is highly regulated, with several major diversion points where water is taken away from its natural course to support agricultural and regional needs. These include the Karakum Canal (which supplies water to Turkmenistan) (Chathuranika et al., 2022), the Kashkadarya Pump Cascade (serving the Kashkadarya region), the Amu-Bukhara Canal (providing water to Bukhara), and the Tuyamuyun Reservoir and Vier system near Nukus (distributing water to the Khorezm and Karakalpakistan regions). A new development — the Qosh-Tepa Canal in Afghanistan — began construction in 2022 and is expected to start withdrawing water for irrigation by 2025. These systems divert water that would otherwise flow to the Aral Sea and instead store it in terminal lakes. On the other hand, the Syr Darya is the longest river in Central Asia, stretching around 3,019 kilometers and draining an area of 219,000 square kilometers. It originates in the Tian Shan Mountains of Kyrgyzstan, where it’s known as the Naryn River until it joins the Kara Darya. The Syr Darya weaves through a complex path — flowing through Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan, briefly entering Tajikistan, returning to Uzbekistan, and finally reaching Kazakhstan. In terms of water withdrawal, the Syr Darya is less diverted compared to the Amu Darya (Ozodbek et al., 2024; Abdullaev et al., 2009). The main known extraction comes from the Aydar-Arnasai lake system, which receives water via a network of irrigation canals and drainage collectors. Additionally, Chardara Reservoir, located on the Uzbekistan-Kazakhstan border, plays a key role in managing water flow, especially during winter months when water is released for downstream use.

Water balance

While the Amu Darya and Syr Darya are the main sources of surface water in Uzbekista, smaller transboundary rivers like Zeravshan, Kashkadarya, Chirchik, and Ahangaran also play important roles. However, most of the flow from rivers like Zeravshan and Kashkadarya is now fully diverted for irrigation, with only occasional runoff reaching desert lakes during very wet years. Uzbekistan’s total annual water consumption is about 51 billion cubic meters, with around

40 billion coming from neighboring countries and just 11 billion from local sources and renewable resources are given in the Table 2. Over the past 30 years, overall water usage has gradually declined. The country also relies heavily on groundwater, with over 12,400 wells in use, about a third managed by the Ministry of Water Resources (Lehner et al., 2008). Additionally, Uzbekistan has 56 reservoirs and 13 debris basins that together can store over 20 billion cubic meters of water.

Table 2. Main water balance parameters (2015-2021 average)

The name of indicator	10⁹ m³/year
Total surface water entering the country	102.2
Outflow to surface water to other countries	99.35
Surface water inflow	65.65
Surface water produced internally	9.54
Groundwater produced internally	8.8
Total internal renewable water resources	16.34
Total renewable groundwater	8.8
Total renewable surface water	42.07
Average water withdrawal	51.5.

Water supply and sanitation in Uzbekistan: Current Challenges

Industrial water use in Uzbekistan is quite low—just under 3%—while domestic and municipal consumption is gradually rising due to population growth and urbanization. Despite progress, the country still faces serious challenges in water supply and sanitation, especially in rural areas (Zuhriddin & Young-Jin, 2023). Much of the water infrastructure dates to the Soviet era and is now in poor condition. Even though government spending has increased in recent years, it hasn't been enough to keep up with the needs for maintenance and expansion. As a result, many regions—particularly outside of cities—struggle with unreliable and low-quality water services. While about 87% of the population has access to piped water (Abdullaev et al., 2009b), only 59% receive safely managed drinking water. The gap is especially noticeable in rural communities, where many rely on wells, untested sources, or aging systems that often supply water for less than half the day. Sanitation is another critical issue (Kulmatov, 2014). Although access to basic sanitation has been widespread for over a decade, centralized sewerage systems are limited. Only around 12% of the population is connected to sewer networks, most of which are concentrated in Tashkent. In other regions, the rate drops to as low as 5%. Many existing treatment facilities are outdated or not operational, causing pollution of rivers and lakes (Berndtsson & Tussupova, 2020; Khasankhanova, n.d.). In rural areas, sanitation is often handled by families themselves using makeshift systems like dry toilets or septic tanks. This situation calls for major investment in water and sanitation infrastructure to improve public health and support sustainable development. Water scarcity remains a major concern, particularly in regions like Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, and Jizzakh, where access to drinking water can fall below 60% and, in some districts, even below 30%. Addressing these disparities is essential for ensuring equal access to clean water across Uzbekistan. While the Amu Darya and Syr Darya are the main sources of surface water in Uzbekistan, smaller transboundary rivers like Zeravshan, Kashkadarya, Chirchik, and Ahangaran also play important roles. However, most of the flow from rivers like Zeravshan and Kashkadarya is now fully diverted for irrigation, with

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Conclusion

Uzbekistan's water resources are facing mounting pressure due to climate change, deteriorating infrastructure, and a heavy reliance on transboundary rivers. Agriculture, which consumes nearly 90% of the country's water, stands at the forefront of the challenge. To address this, the sector must embrace more efficient and sustainable water management practices. The adoption of modern technologies, such as drip irrigation, laser land leveling, and regulated deficit irrigation, offers a viable path forward. These technologies have shown promising results in optimizing water use, improving crop yields, and reducing waste. However, their widespread implementation will require not only technical advancements but also substantial investment, training, and policy support to ensure that they are accessible to farmers across all regions, including those in remote and less economically developed areas.

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